

Auditors' Characteristics and Accounting Information Asymmetry

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ABSTRACT

We contribute to Agency theory by indicating that external auditors can be used strategically to resolve agency conflicts between principals and agents. It is in regard that this paper examines the effects of auditors' characteristics on accounting information asymmetry of 134 listed firms in the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange, over a period of ten years (2013-2022). Auditors' characteristics include auditors' opinion, auditors' independence, audit firm size, auditors' tenure, audit quality (bigfour) and audit rotation. Accounting information asymmetry is measured by Beneish M-Score. Using the Random Effects Model, the results show that auditors' opinion, audit firm size, audit quality (bigfour) and firm size have significant effects on accounting information asymmetry. However, auditors' independence, auditors' tenure, auditors' rotation, leverage and listing age are not significant. The study is limited by the number of samples, specifically 134 companies. It is expected that further research can increase the total sample of companies. Our study results show that the R^2 is 14.27%. Further research is expected to be able to add other auditors' characteristic variables that may influence accounting information quality decisions. Finally, the study makes a major theoretical contribution and suggests that managers should take into consideration, the characteristics of external auditors engaged by their firms. Also, regulators and managers should establish further research opportunities in the areas of auditors' characteristics and accounting information quality. *Keywords:* Accounting Information Asymmetry, Beneish M-Score, Auditors' Characteristics, Listed Firms, Nigerian Exchange

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INTRODUCTION

There is a growing concern about the rising cases of accounting information asymmetry among listed firms in Nigeria. Accounting information quality is a desirable piece of information by corporate investors and other stakeholders, because it guides them in making investment decisions. It essentially defines the value relevance of accounting practices. The whole essence of accounting is to provide quality information to stakeholders. Most corporate stakeholders today are worried about the quality of information they receive from accounting reports and accounts, otherwise refer to as financial statements. From both practice and empirical studies, there are several determinants of accounting information quality. These are easily cited in several literature, including corporate governance, ownership structure, board of directors, women directors, board committees (audit committee, nomination committee, remuneration committee and risk committee), and debt-holders (lenders). However, there are few empirical works on the role of auditors in reducing accounting information asymmetry, particularly in Nigeria. This is the motivation of this study; therefore, this paper aims to examine the effect of auditors' characteristics on accounting information quality.

The role of external auditors in ensuring that financial statements prepared by companies are credible and correct in every sense of the words is a settled principle. External auditors play these roles by conducting independent assessments of the financial statements and disclosures. External auditors are required to confirm that financial statements are errors-free or fraudulent activities or free of any material misstatement. External audit is part of corporate governance mechanisms entrenched in corporations by law, derived from agency theory, in order to ensure that the conflict between shareholders and management is reduced to a barest minimum. In Nigeria, Companies and Allied Matters Act, enacted first in 1990 as Companies and Allied Matters Decree 1, as amended in 2020, provides the legal basis, for the engagement of external auditors. Before then, there was the Companies Act of 1948, which, *inter alia*, requires companies to submit audited reports at the end of every financial years to it and shareholders and creditors. External auditors are operationalized in this study by their characteristics, which include, auditors' opinion, auditors' independence, audit firm size, auditors' tenure, audit quality, and audit rotation.

In addition, three control variables are used in this paper, in order to demonstrate that external auditors are not the only determinant of accounting information quality. They include firm size, leverage and listing age, which are common corporate characteristics, often used in most studies to control for firm specifics, so that the true effects of auditors' characteristics on accounting information quality can be correctly seen. Therefore, this paper examines the role of external auditors in accounting information quality, after controlling for the effects of firm size, leverage and firm listing age. In order to achieve this, the scope of the study is limited to (1) ten (10) years, from 2013 to 2022; (2) the variables used are auditors' opinion, auditors' independence, audit firm size, auditors' tenure, audit quality, and audit rotation as proxies for the independent variable (auditors' characteristics), Beneish M-Score for the dependent variable (accounting information quality) and firm size, leverage and firm listing age as control variables.

Furthermore, a number of stakeholders would find the findings of this paper useful. For example, regulators would be able to use the findings as guide for policy formulation and rules enactment. Shareholders would be able to use the findings as guides in taking investment decisions. Furthermore, members of the boards of directors would be properly guided in directing the affairs of the companies under consideration. In the same vein, members of board committees, such as the audit committee, nomination committee, remuneration committee and risk committee would be guided by the findings of this study. Similarly, lenders (creditors), also known as debt-holders would be properly guided with the findings of this study. In addition, external auditors would be properly guided, specifically, as it refers to their roles in ensuring accounting information quality. Finally, the findings of this study may provide information for performance improvement, further research and a body of knowledge in the areas of auditors' characteristics, accounting information quality, firm size, leverage and firm listing age.

The remaining sections of this paper, include four sections: literature review, methods, results and discussion, conclusions and recommendations. The literature review covers theoretical, conceptual and empirical literature. Also, the methodological section covers the research design, population, sample size, model, variables and their measurements, sources and methods of data, analyses of data and a priori expectations. Section four covers descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and Random Effects Model (REM) regression results. These results are discussed in this section as well. Finally, section five draw conclusions and offer recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Agency Theory, basically, resolves the clash of conflicts of interests arising from the divorce between ownership and control in corporations. Modern corporations are owned by the shareholders, but they are controlled by the management. As a result, in several instances, there are clash of interests between owners (known as principals) and managers (known as agents). So, the role of agency theory is to resolve these conflicts of interests. Agency theory was first developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976). They suggested a theory of how the governance of a firm is based on the conflicts of interest between the firm's owners (shareholders) its managers and major providers of debt capital.

Based on the preceding paragraph, the analytical framework for this study is further explained by the agency theory. The agency theory is the most widely used theory to explain corporate governance mechanisms, of which, external auditors are part. As demonstrated earlier, agency theory is derived from the concept of separation of corporate ownership from control, creating agency crises, among the principals (shareholders), agents (managers) and creditors (lenders of debt capital). The schematic illustration depicted in Figure 1 shows the framework for this study. It illustrates the interaction with the dependent variable (accounting information quality) and the independent variable (auditors' characteristics), proxied with auditors' opinion, auditors' independence, audit firm size, auditors' tenure, audit quality and audit rotation and control variables, proxied with corporate characteristics (which include firm size, leverage and firm listing age). The analytical framework in Figure 1 leads to further articulation of the model specification in methodology section.

Fig 1. Analytical Framework (2023)

In terms of auditors' characteristics, there are various views on the concept. Some authors proxy external auditors' characteristics by auditors' opinion. In conformity with previous studies that measured auditors' opinion (Baldauf & Steckel, 2012; Casterella et al., 2000; Krishnan & Krishnan, 1996; Nieschwietz et al., 2000), this present research employed as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that external auditor place a qualified opinion statement or modified it going concern opinion on the audit report and "0" otherwise as a measure of auditors' opinion (AO). Some others view it from auditors' independence. In this study, consistent with some scholars (Joshi et al., 2007; Kanagaretnam et al., 2010; Li, 2009; Mitra, 2007; Olagunju, 2011; Sarwoko & Agoes, 2014; Shockley, 1981; Sulistiyo et al., 2018; Suseno, 2013), auditors' independence (AI) was operationalised as audit fee or amount paid to auditors divided by total auditors' revenue (%). Furthermore, some other scholars view it from audit firm size. In this study, consistent with some scholars (Ali & Aulia, 2015; Al-Thuneibat et al., 2011; Abedalqader Al-Thuneibat et al., 2011; Dang et al., 2018; Gallo & Christensen, 2011; Kane & Velury, 2004; Rahayu, 2017; Salehi et al., 2009), audit firm size (AFS) was operationalised as natural logarithm of audit fee. Some other scholars view it from auditors' tenure. In this study, consistent with some scholars (Al-Bhoor & Khamees, 2016; Al-Thuneibat et al., 2011; Chi & Huang, 2005; Dao et al., 2008; Kirana & Ramantha, 2020; Krauß & Zülch, 2013; Mgbame et al., 2012; Sinason et al., 2001), auditors' tenure (AT) was operationalised as a dummy where AT is computed as "1" is assigned to companies that use external auditor that have stayed for 3 years and "0" for auditors with less than 3 years of engagement. Still, some other scholars view it from audit quality. In this study, consistent with some scholars (Chi & Huang, 2005; Eisenberg & Macey, 2004; Knechel et al., 2013; Kwon et al., 2014; Law, 2008; Rahayu, 2017; Rahman et al., 2019; Salleh & Jasmani, 2014; Samaha & Hegazy, 2010), audit quality (AQ, also known as Big4) was operationalised as a dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that use PWC, Deloitte, E&Y and KPMG as external auditors and "0" otherwise. Finally, other scholars view it as auditors' rotation (switching) where auditors' rotation (AR) is computed as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that change external auditor in a particular year and "0" otherwise, which is in agreement with some scholars (Chi & Huang, 2005; Chung, 2004; Hai & Quy, 2019; Horton et al., 2011; Kirana & Ramantha, 2020; Kwon et al., 2014; Lowensohn et al., 2007; Mardini & Tahat, 2017; Polychronidou et al., 2020; Salleh & Jasmani, 2014).

In terms of accounting information quality, there are several views on the concept. Some scholars called it financial reporting quality (Al-Shaer, 2020; Bradshaw et al., 1999; Chalaki et al., 2012; Felo et al., 2003; Gebrayel et al., 2018; He et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2021; Paulinus et al., 2017), some others call it accounting quality (Barth et al., 2008; Ibadin & Dabor, 2015; Hribar et al., 2014; Imhoff Jr, 1992; Liu et al., 2011; Marquardt & Zur, 2015; Paiva & Lourenço, 2010; Pășcan, 2015; Schumann et al., 2023; Velte & Stiglbauer, 2011). Still, some scholars call it earnings management (Baba & Yahaya, 2023; Ibrahim et al., 2019; Itopa et al., 2022; Jegede et al., 2018; Kasanen et al., 1996; McNichols, 2000; Yahaya, 2022; Yahaya & Abdulfatah, 2022; Yahaya et al., 2015). Yet, some other scholars call it earnings quality (Andrew et al., 2018; Bouaziz et al., 2020; Gulzar, 2011; Kamarudin & Ismail, 2014; Kasanen et al., 1996; McNichols, 2000; Palacios-Manzano et al., 2021; Persakis & Iatridis, 2015; Shuto, 2007; Sun & Rath, 2008; Vander Bauwhede & Willekens, 2003; Yahaya et al., 2017). However, in this paper, and in consistent with scholars (Elaoud & Jarboui, 2017; Hu et al., 2012; Mamić Sačer & Oluić, 2013; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2020; Phomlaphatrachakom, 2020; Ren, 2016; Wongsim & Gao, 2011; Xu, 2015), we would refer to it as accounting information quality, measured by Beneish Fraud M-Score, measured as $-4.84 + 0.92$ (Sales Debtor Index) $+ 0.528$ (Gross Profit Index) $+ 0.404$ (Other Asset Index) $+ 0.892$ (Sales Growth Index) $+ 0.115$ (Depreciation Index) $- 0.172$ (Expenses Index) $+ 4.679$ (Total Accrual Index) $- 0.327$ (Leverage Index). There are several other measures of accounting information quality that are not adopted in this study. However, for the purpose of information, they include De Angelo Score, Jones Discretionary Accrual Score, Modified Jones Discretionary Score, Dechow and Dichev Discretionary Score, Yoon, Kim and Woodruff Discretionary Accrual Score, Larcker and Richardson Discretionary Accrual Score, Kothari Discretionary Accrual Score, and Rowchowdhury Real Earnings Management Score. In terms of control variables, firm size (FS) is the natural logarithm of total assets, as used by (Abedalqader Al-Thuneibat et al., 2011; Arvanitis, 1997; Bansal, 2021; Canback et al., 2006; Dang et al., 2018; Shefer & Frenkel, 2005; Yahaya, 2006; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021). Furthermore, leverage (LEV) is total liabilities divided by total assets, as used by some scholars (Awen & Yahaya, 2023; Itopa et al., 2019; Samaila et al., 2023; Yahaya & Andow, 2015; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021). Firm listing age (FLA) is measured as number of years a company is traded with the stock exchange, as measured by (Bansal, 2021; Coad, 2018; Variyam & Kraybill, 1992; Wöhrle et al., 2009; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021).

In order to understand the relationship between auditors' characteristics and accounting information quality, there are several studies conducted in and outside Nigeria. For example, Johnson et al. (2010) examine whether the length of the relationship between audit-firm tenure and financial-reporting quality. Using two proxies for financial-reporting quality and a sample of Big 6 clients matched on industry and size, we find that relative to medium audit-firm tenures of four to eight years, short audit-firm tenures of two to three years are associated with lower-quality financial reports. In contrast, we find no evidence of reduced financial-reporting quality for longer audit-firm tenures of nine or more years.

Soliman (2014) investigate the impact of auditors' characteristics, which is characterized by audit firm size and auditor tenure on accounting information quality in the financial reports of the more active 50 non-financial companies listed at Egyptian Stock Exchange across four years of period from 2007 to 2010. After controlling for company size and leverage, the results show that audit firm size and auditor tenure have significant positive relation with accounting information quality. On the other hand, no significant relationship is found between company size and accounting information quality.

Mohammad and Ahmed (2017) examine the relationship between external auditors' characteristics and financial reporting quality of top 100 firms from Bursa Malaysia. The analysis of annual reports proves that large audit firms do not have any significant effect on financial reporting quality. Ali et al. (2019) examine the impact of big4 audit firm the financial reporting quality of 233 observations for many firms listed in the Iraqi stock exchange and cover the period 2014-2018. The study results reveal an insignificant relationship between big4 audit firm and the financial reporting quality.

Farouk et al. (2019) examine the effect of external Auditors' attributes on financial reporting quality of listed Consumer Goods firms in Nigeria for eighteen firms listed under the Consumer Goods firms in Nigerian Stock Exchange for the period 2010-2015. The findings revealed that audit firm size and audit tenure have significant negative effect on financial reporting quality of firms. Abdollahi et al. (2020) examine the effect of audit firm size on accounting information quality of companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange during the years 2008–2017. The study includes a sample of 1,530 firm-year observations. The findings reveal that

audit firm size is positively and significantly correlated with accounting information quality.

Soroushyar (2022) examines the relationship between auditor characteristics and financial reporting quality. This study includes 1,450 firm-year observations and 145 companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) over a ten-year period from 2011 to 2020. The results show that auditor tenure has a positive association with financial reporting quality. Lamido et al. (2022) examine the effects of audit firm characteristics on the financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria of 12 consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group for 15 years (2006 to 2020). Multiple regression analysis results reveal that auditor opinion, audit tenure and audit rotation have positive significant effects on financial reporting quality. On the other hand, auditor independence and audit quality show insignificant effects.

Usman and Ugoh (2023) examine the connection between external auditor characteristics and financial reporting quality of 29 quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for 2011 to 2020. From the regression results, it was revealed that audit firm size has a statistically positive significant effect on financial reporting quality while auditor tenure was found to have no significant influence on the financial reporting quality.

METHODOLOGY

This research followed the Agency Theory to arrive at a rational conclusion by logical generalization from a known fact. The unit of analysis of this study was the 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange and the research was in the form of a panel data study. The current study is grounded on positivism, and is a non-contrived study (Saunders et al., 2009). With the quantitative approach to the study, data was gathered using annual reports and accounts of a sample of 134 listed firms.

Auditors' characteristics consist of six basic dimensions: auditors' opinion, auditors' independence, audit firm size, audit quality (big4), audit tenure and audit rotation. Each dimension was measured in a different way (see Table 1). The research focused particularly on the effects of auditors' characteristics on accounting information quality. Similarly, accounting information quality was measured using Beneish Fraud M-Score, while three control variables: firm size (natural logarithm of total assets), leverage (total liabilities divided by total assets) and firm listing age (date of listing to 31 December 2022) were included in the model.

Table 1 Operationalization/measurement of variables and expected signs

Variables	Notation and Sources	A priori Sign
Y- Accounting information quality	Measured as $-4.84+0.92(\text{Sales Debtor Index})+0.528(\text{Gross Profit Index})+0.404(\text{Other Asset Index})+0.892(\text{Sales Growth Index})+0.115(\text{Depreciation Index})-0.172(\text{Expenses Index})+4.679(\text{Total Accrual Index})-0.327(\text{Leverage Index})$	
X ₁ : Auditors' Opinion	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that external auditor place a qualified opinion statement or modified it going concern opinion on the audit report and "0" otherwise	-
X ₂ : Auditors' independence	Measured as audit fee or amount paid to auditors divided by revenue (%)	+
X ₃ : Audit firm size	Measured as log of total audit fee	+
X ₄ : Audit quality (Big4)	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that use PWC, Deloitte, E&Y and KPMG as external auditors and "0" otherwise	+
X ₅ : Audit Tenure	Measured as dummy where is computed as "1" is assigned to companies that use external auditor that have stayed for 3 years and "0" for auditors with less than 3 years of engagement	-
X ₆ : Audit Rotation	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that change external auditor in a particular year and "0" otherwise	+
X ₇ : Firm size	Natural logarithm of total assets	+/-
X ₈ : Leverage	Total liabilities divided by total assets	+/-
X ₉ : Firm listing age	Measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange	+/-

Source: *Author's Compilation (2023)*

In this study, the model was specified to capture auditors' characteristics and accounting information quality. Thus, the study adapted the model specified by Usman and Ugoh (2023) which was modified for the purpose of establishing the relationship between dependent variables and the linear combinations of several independent variables captured in the study. The model reflects the

identified six (6) auditors' characteristics and the one (1) proxy of accounting information quality. The model was specified as:

$$AIQ_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AO_{i,t} + \beta_2 AI_{i,t} + \beta_3 AFS_{i,t} + \beta_4 AQ_{i,t} + \beta_5 AT_{i,t} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t} + \beta_7 FS_{i,t} + \beta_8 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_9 FLA_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

AIQ = Accounting information quality

AO = Auditors' Opinion

AI = Auditors' Independence

AFS = Audit Firm Size

AQ = Audit Quality

AT = Audit Tenure

AR = Audit Rotation (Switching)

FS = Firm Size

LEV = Leverage

FLA = Firm Listing Age

i = Firm Script (in this case, i = 134)

t = Time Script (in this case, t = 10 years)

β_0 = Intercept (constant)

β_{1-9} = Beta Coefficients

ϵ = Idiosyncratic Error Term

Thus, our a priori expectations are stated as:

Whereas:

$X_1 > 0$: A modified auditor's opinion will lead to a reduction in accounting information quality;

$X_2 > 0$: A rise in auditor's independence will lead to an increase in accounting information quality;

$X_3 > 0$: An expansion in audit firm size will lead to a corresponding rise in accounting information quality;

$X_4 > 0$: A rise in audit quality will lead to a corresponding rise accounting information quality;

$X_5 > 0$: A rise in audit tenure will lead to a corresponding reduction in accounting information quality; and

$X_6 > 0$: A rise in audit rotation will lead to a corresponding rise accounting information quality.

The econometric technique adopted in this study is Panel Random Effects regression technique. The rationale for its usage is based on the following justifications: the data that was collected have time and cross-sectional attributes that gives room for studying the variables of interest over time (time series) as well as across the sampled firms (cross-section); panel data regression provides better results since it increases sample size and reduces the problem of degree of freedom (Muhammad, 2012); it avoids the problem of multicollinearity and help to capture the individual cross-sectional (or firm-specific) effects that the various pools may exhibit with respect to the dependent variable in the model.

Hausman and Taylor (1981) also recommended panel data estimation method because it enables a cross-sectional time series analysis which usually makes provision for a broader set of data points, but also because of its ability to control heterogeneity and endogeneity issues. Hence panel data estimation allows for the control of individual-specific effects usually unobservable which may be correlated with other explanatory variables included in the specification of the relationship between dependent and explanatory variables. In evaluating the panel regression results, the Hausman specification test was used to select between fixed effect and random effect. The individual statistical significance test (T-test) and overall statistical significance test (F-test) are used. Importantly, the goodness of fit of the model are ascertained using the coefficient of determination (R^2). Our panel analysis is done after descriptive statistics and correlation matrix.

FINDINGS

Data were analysed for descriptive statistics and the results are reported in Table 2 as follows.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
AIQ	1340	-2.426	1.351	-5.42	9.06
AO	1340	.033	.18	0	1
AI	1340	.579	.036	.434	.697
AFS	1340	4.335	.448	2.683	5.795
AT	1340	.694	.462	0	1
AQ	1340	.878	.328	0	1
AR	1340	.117	.322	0	1
FS	1340	7.482	.724	5.39	8.68
LEV	1340	65.383	27.911	4.28	305.8
LAGE	1340	27.067	10.007	2	48

Source: STATA 15.1

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 for the variables show that the number of observations is 1,340, meaning that 134 listed firms multiplied by ten (10) years. Furthermore, it shows that the mean of accounting information quality is -2.426, the mean of auditors' opinion is .033, the mean of auditors' independence is .579 (57.9 percent), the mean of audit firm size is 4.335 points, the mean of audit tenure is .694, the mean of audit quality (big4) is .878, and the mean of audit rotation is .117. On the control variables, the mean of firm size is 7.482, the mean of leverage is 65.383 percent, and the mean of firm listing age is 27 years.

In terms of spread (standard deviation), the standard deviation of accounting information quality is 1.351, the standard deviation of auditors' opinion is .18, the standard deviation of auditors independence is .036, the standard deviation of audit firm size is .448, the standard deviation of audit tenure is .462, the standard deviation of audit quality is .328, the standard deviation of audit rotation is .322, the standard deviation of firm size is .724, the standard deviation of leverage is 27.91 percent, and the standard deviation of firm listing age is 10 years.

In terms of minimum mean, accounting information quality is -5.42, the minimum mean of auditors' opinion is 0, the minimum mean of auditors independence is .434, the minimum mean of audit firm size is 2.683, the minimum mean of audit tenure is 0, the minimum mean of audit quality is 0, the minimum mean of audit rotation is 0, the minimum mean of firm size is 5.39, the minimum mean of leverage is 4.28 percent, and the minimum mean of firm listing age is 2 years. In terms of maximum mean, accounting information quality is 9.06, the maximum mean of auditors' opinion is 1, the maximum mean of auditors independence is .697, the maximum mean of audit firm size is 5.795, the maximum mean of audit tenure is 1, the maximum mean of audit quality is 1, the maximum mean of audit rotation is 1, the maximum mean of firm size is 8.68, the maximum mean of leverage is 305.8 percent, and the maximum mean of firm listing age is 48 years.

Furthermore, the Pearson correlation coefficient matrix is used to identify the direction and strength of the relationship between the auditors' characteristics and accounting information quality. The results are contained in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3 *Pairwise correlations*

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) AIQ	1.000									
(2) AO	-0.038 (0.613)	1.000								
(3) AI	0.008 (0.912)	0.162* (0.029)	1.000							
(4) AFS	-0.098 (0.191)	-0.305* (0.000)	0.262* (0.000)	1.000						
(5) AT	0.107 (0.152)	-0.213* (0.004)	0.045 (0.546)	0.143 (0.056)	1.000					
(6) AQ	-0.312* (0.000)	-0.309* (0.000)	-0.080 (0.284)	0.405* (0.000)	0.047 (0.531)	1.000				
(7) AR	-0.021 (0.783)	-0.067 (0.368)	0.018 (0.806)	0.063 (0.398)	-0.473* (0.000)	0.030 (0.690)	1.000			
(8) FS	-0.057 (0.449)	-0.285* (0.000)	-0.187* (0.012)	0.841* (0.000)	0.069 (0.356)	0.370* (0.000)	0.075 (0.315)	1.000		
(9) LEV	0.034 (0.653)	0.624* (0.000)	0.168* (0.024)	-0.252* (0.001)	-0.262* (0.000)	-0.365* (0.000)	0.067 (0.369)	-0.316* (0.000)	1.000	
(10) LAGE	-0.006 (0.941)	0.104 (0.164)	-0.005 (0.945)	-0.044 (0.562)	0.031 (0.679)	0.025 (0.743)	0.020 (0.789)	-0.098 (0.190)	0.057 (0.447)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 15.1

As indicated in Table 3, auditors' opinion has negative correlation with accounting information quality. This is in consistent with our a priori expectation. Furthermore, auditors' independence shows a positive correlation with accounting information quality. This is consistent with our a priori expectation. Audit firm size shows a negative correlation with accounting information quality. This is not consistent with our a priori expectation. We expect an expansion in audit firm size to deliver improvement in accounting information quality. This may be caused by entropy and or inability of the firms to take advantage of economies of size and scope.

Audit tenure is positively correlated with accounting information quality. This is not consistent with our a priori expectation, however, it may be as a result of benefit of experience and exposure that come with long years of engagement. Also, audit quality (big4) is negatively significant with accounting information quality. While we expect this bivariate relationship to be significant, we are not expecting it to be negative. However, this can be rationalized by the recent failure of Arthur Anderson, which opens up debate on the superiority of the big four (big4) audit firms. Audit rotation shows negative correlation with accounting information quality. This result may happen as a result of change from big4 audit firms to non-big4 audit firms and vice versa, which may cause temporary setback.

Firm size shows negative correlation with accounting information quality. This result is consistent with our a priori expectation. Large size may not provide offer any particular advantage, Union Bank of Nigeria, which was recently taken by little known Titan Trust bank is a reference point to remember. Leverage shows a positive correlation with accounting information quality. This result is consistent with our a priori expectation. Highly geared firms are usually in dare need of capital, which may be provided by current or potential shareholders and these shareholders need to be motivated by high quality accounting information. Finally, listing age shows negative correlation with accounting information quality. This is also consistent with our a priori expectation. Age may not confer any superior advantage. Several old firms have failed in Nigeria; the case of Bata (a shoe making company) and several textile companies are cases of reference.

The Random Effects Model (REM) regression results for the equation are given Table 4.

Table 4 REM Regression Results

AIQ	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf. Interval]
AO	-1.407	.7608066	-1.85	0.064	-2.89822 .0840868
AI	6.862	5.001616	1.37	0.170	-2.941444 16.66453
AFS	-1.252238	.7491003	-1.67	0.095	-2.720447 .2159718
AT	.3854345	.252424	1.53	0.127	-.1093074 .8801765
AQ	-1.332064	.3460172	-3.85	0.000	-2.010245 -.6538825
AR	.1126575	.3493503	0.32	0.747	-.5720564 .7973715
FS	.7520866	.432583	1.74	0.082	-.0957605 1.599934
LEV	.0026687	.0047721	0.56	0.576	-.0066844 .0120218
LAGE	.0049334	.0099015	0.50	0.618	-.0144732 .0243399
_cons	-5.972549	3.207585	-1.86	0.063	-12.2593 .3142014

R² Overall = .1427

Wald chi²(9) = 28.30

Prob > chi² = .0008

Source: STATA 15.1

As indicated in Table 4, in terms of effects, the effect of auditors' opinion is negative, however, the beta coefficient implies that for every unit opinion expressed by the auditor(s), there is a corresponding reduction in accounting information quality by 1.407 points. In contrast, the effect of auditors' independence on accounting information quality is positive. In addition, for every effort to ensure that auditors are independent, the corresponding increase in accounting information quality is 6.862 points. The effect of audit firm size is negative, however, for every unit rise in audit firm size, the corresponding reduction in accounting information quality is 1.252. The effect of audit tenure is positive, however, for every change in audit tenure produces a corresponding positive effect on accounting information

quality by .385. The effect of audit quality is negative, however, for every change of auditor(s), either from big4 or non-big4, the corresponding reduction in accounting information quality is 1.332. The effect of audit rotation is positive, however, for every rotation or switching of auditors, accounting information quality improves by .113. On the control variables, the effect of firm size is positive, however, for unit expansion of audit firm, the corresponding increase in accounting information quality is .752. The effect of leverage is positive, however, for every increase in debt, the corresponding improvement in accounting information quality is .0027. The effect of firm listing age is positive, however, for every year of maturity and experience gained by the audit firm, accounting information quality improves by a little .0049 points.

In terms of significant effects, auditors' opinion shows a significant effect on accounting information quality at 10 percent. Auditors' independence shows an insignificant effect on accounting information quality. Also, audit firm size shows a significant effect on accounting information quality at 10 percent. Audit tenure shows an insignificant effect on accounting information quality. Audit quality shows a significant effect on accounting information quality at 1 percent. Furthermore, audit rotation shows an insignificant effect on accounting information quality. On the control variables, firm size shows a significant effect on accounting information quality at 10 percent. Leverage shows an insignificant effect on accounting information quality. In the same vein, firm listing age shows an insignificant effect on accounting information quality.

DISCUSSION, IMPLICATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

Outcome of this study reveals that a significant effect was found between auditors' opinion and accounting information quality. This result confirms our a priori expectation and previous research studies (Baldauf & Steckel, 2012; Casterella et al., 2000; Krishnan & Krishnan, 1996; Nieschwietz et al., 2000). The study also revealed that, audit firm size impacts accounting information quality. This result confirms our a priori expectation and previous research studies (Ali & Aulia, 2015; Al-Thuneibat et al., 2011; Abedalqader Al-Thuneibat et al., 2011; Dang et al., 2018; Gallo & Christensen, 2011; Kane & Velury, 2004; Rahayu, 2017; Salehi et al., 2009). In the same vein, the study also revealed that, audit quality (big4) impacts accounting information quality. This result confirms our a priori expectation and previous research studies (Chi & Huang, 2005; Eisenberg & Macey,

2004; Knechel et al., 2013; Kwon et al., 2014; Law, 2008; Rahayu, 2017; Rahman et al., 2019; Salleh & Jasmani, 2014; Samaha & Hegazy, 2010). The study also revealed that firm size impacts accounting information quality. This result confirms our a priori expectation and previous research studies (Abedalqader Al-Thuneibat et al., 2011; Arvanitis, 1997; Bansal, 2021; Canback et al., 2006; Dang et al., 2018; Shefer & Frenkel, 2005; Yahaya, 2006; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021).

The findings revealed that there is a significant effect of auditors' opinion on accounting information quality (H₁). Thus, hypothesis one is hereby rejected. Also, the findings revealed that there is no significant effect of auditors' independence on accounting information quality (H₂). Thus, hypothesis two is hereby accepted. The findings revealed that there is a significant effect of audit firm size on accounting information quality (H₃). Thus, hypothesis three is hereby rejected. Also, the findings revealed that there is no significant effect of auditors' tenure on accounting information quality (H₄). Thus, hypothesis four is hereby accepted. The findings revealed that there is a significant effect of audit quality on accounting information quality (H₅). Thus, hypothesis five is hereby rejected. Also, the findings revealed that there is no significant effect of auditors' rotation (switching) on accounting information quality (H₆). Thus, hypothesis six is hereby accepted.

Theoretical Contribution

This paper examined the effects of auditors' characteristics on accounting information quality across 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange, from 2013 to 2022 using the agency theory, which brings in the auditor to resolve the conflict of interests between the shareholders and managers. The findings of the current study revealed that the joint effects of auditors' characteristics are significant on accounting information quality (Prob>chi² is .0008).

Managerial Implications

Firstly, the study advocates responsive relationship between the auditors and managers, in order to avoid negative auditors' opinion about the accounts and reports presented by managers. Secondly, this paper provides useful information to companies to select from large size audit firms for the purpose of audit. Large audit firms have the resources, know-how,

competence, economies of scope and scale to ensure that quality is provided in their audit. Thirdly, this paper provides useful information to companies to select from big4 audit firms. Big4 audit firms are large and have the resources, connection, networks, experience, exposure, know-how, competence, economies of scope and scale to ensure that quality is provided in their audit. Fourthly, this study provides a practical understanding on how to deal with auditors in terms of their characteristics such as independence, tenure, and rotation. Fifthly, this study has shown that not only auditors' characteristics affect accounting information quality, which were the roles firm size, leverage and firm listing age were designed to serve in this study; they equally affect accounting information quality. Finally, this study provides a practical understanding of the characteristics of external auditors and their roles in determining accounting information quality.

Limitations and Further Research

There are a few limitations in this study which can be examined by future research. One limitation is that the findings of the research are based on 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange, out of the 156 listed firms, altogether. Another limitation of this study is that the data used are obtained for ten (10) years, covering 2013 to 2022. The variables used to proxy auditors' characteristics are six (6), future research can expand these numbers to include auditors' busyness, specialization, international experience, and joint audit. Furthermore, accounting information quality is proxied by the Beneish Fraud M-Score. Other proxies for accounting information quality are available, including the De Angelo Discretionary Accrual Score, Jones Discretionary Accrual Score, Modified Jones Discretionary Accrual Score, Change in Working Capital Model, Dechow and Dichev Model, and Rowchowdhury Real Earnings Management Score. Three control variables are used, such as firm size, firm leverage, and firm listing age. Other control variables are available, that affect accounting information quality, such as profitability, liquidity, asset tangibility, ownership structure, board characteristics, and board committees. Future studies can also consider on several countries instead of Nigeria, alone.

CONCLUSION

The aim of this paper was to ascertain the impact of auditors' characteristics on accounting information quality based on the agency theory. The findings of this study corroborated the existing empirical evidence that supports the direct relationship between some auditors' characteristics and accounting information quality. Furthermore, auditors' opinion, audit firm size and audit quality were found to have significant effects on accounting information. In contrast, auditors' independence, auditors' tenure, and audit rotation were found not to have significant effects on accounting information quality. Therefore, this paper posits that the impact of auditors' characteristics on accounting information quality is mixed across multi companies.

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